

EXPLORING SECTOR-SPECIFIC PROGRESS IN WHOLESALE AND RETAIL TRADE, MOTOR VEHICLE, AND MOTORCYCLE REPAIR IN THE ROMANIAN MOUNTAINOUS REGION FROM 2008 TO 2018

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Introduction:

The economic landscape of the Romanian mountainous region has undergone significant transformations in recent years, particularly in sectors such as wholesale and retail trade, motor vehicle, and motorcycle repair. This article delves into a comprehensive analysis of the developments within these sectors from 2008 to 2018, shedding light on the trends, challenges, and growth patterns that have shaped the business environment in this unique geographic setting.

Methodology:

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The study employs rigorous statistical methodologies, including normality tests and logarithmization, to ensure the reliability of the results. The importance of these tests lies in their ability to discern the influences of various factors on the evolution of the economic sectors under consideration. Parametric tests are then applied, taking into account the distribution of scores within normal limits, as per the working hypothesis.

Central Tendency and Growth Dynamics:

The central tendency analysis for the period from 2008 to 2018 demonstrates a notable increase in the population of active enterprises in the studied sector. Despite a decrease in the growth rate, the hypothesis of intensification of activity is verified. The statistics, coupled with the accompanying histogram, confirm both a moderate crowding and a discernible trend of abandonment within this sector in Romania. Simultaneously, there is evidence supporting a reduction in the rate of growth of this economic sector segment.

Sector-Specific Trends:

The statistical data for the wholesale and retail trade, motor vehicle, and motorcycle repair segments in the Romanian mountainous region reveal

intriguing sector-specific trends. An in-depth examination of figures and the Parametric Analysis Romania appendix highlights a mean of 22,625.82 with a standard error of 2,996.174. The distribution curve appears centrally symmetric, concentrating scores around the mean, and exhibits leptokurtosis, indicating a certain degree of statistical significance.

The statistical analysis for the sectors encompassing wholesale and retail trade, along with the repair of motor vehicles and motorcycles (refer to figures 2.4.1 – 2.4.5 and appendices chapter 2), reveals a consistent increase in the mean and median values for each sector individually. However, other statistical indicators display occasional antagonistic fluctuations, encompassing values such as Mean, Std. Error of Mean, Median, Std. Deviation, Skewness, Kurtosis, Variance, Minimum, Maximum, and Percentile 50 Value, reiterated for each specific indicator. Noteworthy figures include a mean of 263,245.22, standard error at mean of 5,551.789, and a median of 271,459.00, among others.

These presented values illustrate the positive development of the wholesale and retail trade sector, as well as the repair of motor vehicles and motorcycles in the mountainous regions of Romania, concerning the population of active enterprises. Despite some sectors exhibiting negative values, the overall portrayal indicates a favorable business environment for

the industry within the mountainous areas.

The significance of the conducted tests lies in their ability to meticulously scrutinize the influences of specific factors on the evolution of the wholesale and retail trade, motor vehicle, and motorcycle repair sectors. After applying normality tests and logarithmization, the null hypothesis is rejected, paving the way for the analysis of the working hypothesis. Descriptive and inferential analysis considers the distribution of scores within normal limits, for which parametric tests are applied.

The central trend observed in the wholesale and retail trade, repair of motor vehicles, and motorcycles sectors of the economy during the analyzed period reveals a substantial growth in the population of active enterprises in mountainous Romania from 2008 to 2019. The statistics associated with this indicator depict a high degree of non-variability, signifying minimal deviation and positive outcomes. Symmetrical distributions suggest a considerable stabilization of the business environment throughout the examined period, with kurtosis, characterized by a low standard error, indicating concentration in certain industries.

Figure 2.4.1. The evolution of mountain entrepreneurship in Romania for S4 in the period 2008-2019

Figure 2.4.2. The evolution of mountain entrepreneurship in Macroregion one of Romania for S4 in the period 2008-2019

Figure 2.4.3. The evolution of mountain entrepreneurship in Macroregion two of Romania for S4 in the period 2008-2019

Figure 2.4.4. The evolution of mountain entrepreneurship in the third Macroregion of Romania for S4 in the period 2008-2019

Figure 2.4.5. The evolution of mountain entrepreneurship in the fourth Macroregion of Romania for S4 in the period 2008-2019

The predictive analysis for the secondary, tertiary, and quaternary sectors in the mountainous regions of Romania suggests a sustained growth trajectory until the year 2030 (table 1). Whether at the national, macro-regional, regional, or county level, models derived from statistical analyses reveal variations in sustainability across different mountainous areas. Harmonization statistics provide essential values for mean, standard error, minimum, maximum, and 5/10 percentiles (presented in sequence), as outlined below:

- Stationary R-squared: -.045, .038, -.163, .027, -.106, -.095
- R-squared: .595, .175, .086, 1.000, .200, .350
- RMSE: 1,206,241, 1,942,077, .000, 13,181,442, 155,526, 215,111
- MAPS: 5,638, 1,905, .000, 10,811, 2,603, 2,875
- MaxAPE: 23.023, 9.064, .000, 47.625, 9.010, 10.947
- MAE: 713,889, 1,072,976, .000, 7,254,554, 104,122, 144,529
- MaxAE: 3,045,695, 4,980,770, .000, 33,841,016, 345,796, 511,718
- Normalized BIC: 13,306, 1,929, 10,200, 19,217, 10,396, 11,027

These metrics provide valuable insights into the sustainability and variation of the forecasted growth patterns, offering a comprehensive understanding of the future trends in the mountainous sectors of Romania.

Conclusion:

This article provides a nuanced exploration of sector-specific advancements in wholesale and retail trade, motor vehicle, and motorcycle repair within the Romanian mountainous region. The findings underscore the complex interplay of factors influencing economic evolution, and the insights gained contribute to a more profound understanding of the business landscape in this unique geographic context.

Table 1. Forecast analysis of mountain entrepreneurship in the mountain area of Romania for S4

Model		Forecast										
		2020	2021	2022	2023	2024	2025	2026	2027	2028	2029	2030
Romania-Model_1	Forecast	26116	26116	26116	26116	26116	26116	26116	26116	26116	26116	26116
	UCL	29156	30415	31381	32196	32913	33562	34159	34714	35235	35729	36198
	LCL	23077	21818	20852	20037	19320	18671	18074	17519	16998	16504	16035
Macroregiuneaunu-Model_2	Forecast	64173	64173	64173	64173	64173	64173	64173	64173	64173	64173	64173
	UCL	70685	73382	75451	77196	78733	80123	81400	82590	83707	84764	85769
	LCL	57661	54964	52895	51150	49613	48224	46946	45756	44639	43583	42578
Nord-Vest-Model_3	Forecast	34559	34559	34559	34559	34559	34559	34559	34559	34559	34559	34559
	UCL	40376	42786	44635	46194	47567	48809	49950	51013	52011	52955	53853
	LCL	28742	26332	24483	22924	21551	20309	19168	18105	17107	16163	15265
Bihor-Model_4	Forecast	8524	8524	8524	8524	8524	8524	8524	8524	8524	8524	8524
	UCL	9930	10512	10959	11336	11668	11968	12243	12500	12742	12970	13187
	LCL	7118	6536	6089	5712	5380	5080	4805	4548	4307	4078	3861
Bistrita-Nasaud-Model_5	Forecast	3652	3652	3652	3652	3652	3652	3652	3652	3652	3652	3652
	UCL	4352	4642	4865	5052	5218	5367	5504	5632	5752	5866	5974
	LCL	2952	2662	2439	2252	2086	1937	1800	1672	1552	1438	1330
Cluj-Model_6	Forecast	9917	9917	9917	9917	9917	9917	9917	9917	9917	9917	9917
	UCL	11221	11762	12176	12526	12834	13112	13368	13606	13830	14042	14243
	LCL	8613	8072	7658	7308	7000	6722	6466	6228	6004	5792	5591
Maramures-Model_7	Forecast	5884	5884	5884	5884	5884	5884	5884	5884	5884	5884	5884
	UCL	7252	7818	8253	8620	8943	9235	9503	9753	9988	10210	10421
	LCL	4516	3950	3515	3148	2825	2533	2265	2015	1780	1558	1347

Satu Model_8	Mare- Forecast	3573	3573	3573	3573	3573	3573	3573	3573	3573	3573	3573	3573
	UCL	4230	4502	4710	4886	5041	5181	5310	5430	5543	5650	5751	
	LCL	2916	2644	2436	2260	2105	1965	1836	1716	1603	1496	1395	
Salaj-Model_9	Forecast	3108	3207	3306	3405	3504	3602	3701	3800	3899	3998	4097	
	UCL	3742	4103	4404	4673	4921	5155	5379	5593	5801	6003	6200	
	LCL	2474	2310	2208	2137	2086	2049	2024	2007	1997	1993	1994	
Centru-Model_10	Forecast	29614	29614	29614	29614	29614	29614	29614	29614	29614	29614	29614	29614
	UCL	34874	37052	38724	40133	41375	42497	43530	44490	45393	46246	47058	
	LCL	24354	22176	20504	19095	17853	16731	15699	14738	13835	12982	12170	
Alba-Model_11	Forecast	4086	4086	4086	4086	4086	4086	4086	4086	4086	4086	4086	4086
	UCL	5105	5527	5850	6123	6364	6581	6781	6967	7142	7307	7465	
	LCL	3067	2645	2322	2049	1808	1591	1391	1205	1030	865	707	
Brasov-Model_12	Forecast	7457	7457	7457	7457	7457	7457	7457	7457	7457	7457	7457	7457
	UCL	8495	8925	9255	9533	9778	9999	10203	10393	10571	10739	10899	
	LCL	6419	5989	5659	5381	5136	4915	4711	4521	4343	4175	4015	
Covasna-Model_13	Forecast	2281	2281	2281	2281	2281	2281	2281	2281	2281	2281	2281	2281
	UCL	2720	2901	3041	3158	3262	3355	3442	3522	3597	3668	3736	
	LCL	1842	1661	1521	1404	1300	1207	1121	1040	965	894	826	
Harghita-Model_14	Forecast	4024	4024	4024	4024	4024	4024	4024	4024	4024	4024	4024	4024
	UCL	4895	5256	5533	5766	5972	6158	6328	6488	6637	6778	6913	
	LCL	3153	2792	2515	2282	2076	1890	1720	1560	1411	1270	1135	
Mures-Model_15	Forecast	6962	6962	6962	6962	6962	6962	6962	6962	6962	6962	6962	6962
	UCL	8183	8689	9077	9405	9693	9953	10193	10416	10626	10824	11012	
	LCL	5741	5235	4847	4520	4231	3971	3731	3508	3298	3100	2912	
Sibiu-Model_16	Forecast	4804	4804	4804	4804	4804	4804	4804	4804	4804	4804	4804	4804
	UCL	5633	5976	6239	6461	6657	6834	6997	7148	7290	7425	7553	
	LCL	3975	3632	3369	3147	2951	2774	2611	2460	2318	2183	2056	

Macroregiunea doi-Model_17	Forecast	70675	70675	70675	70675	70675	70675	70675	70675	70675	70675	70675
	UCL	80754	84929	88133	90834	93213	95364	97342	99183	100913	102548	104104
	LCL	60596	56421	53217	50517	48137	45986	44008	42167	40437	38802	37246
Nord-Est-Model_18	Forecast	38264	38264	38264	38264	38264	38264	38264	38264	38264	38264	38264
	UCL	46859	50420	53152	55455	57484	59318	61005	62576	64050	65445	66772
	LCL	29669	26108	23376	21073	19044	17210	15523	13952	12478	11083	9756
Bacau-Model_19	Forecast	7046	7046	7046	7046	7046	7046	7046	7046	7046	7046	7046
	UCL	8691	9372	9895	10335	10724	11075	11398	11698	11980	12247	12501
	LCL	5401	4720	4197	3757	3368	3017	2694	2394	2112	1845	1591
Botosani-Model_20	Forecast	3805	3805	3805	3805	3805	3805	3805	3805	3805	3805	3805
	UCL	4954	5363	5686	5960	6204	6424	6628	6818	6997	7166	7327
	LCL	2657	2247	1925	1650	1407	1186	983	793	614	445	284
Iasi-Model_21	Forecast	9713	9713	9713	9713	9713	9713	9713	9713	9713	9713	9713
	UCL	11610	12396	12999	13507	13955	14359	14732	15078	15404	15711	16004
	LCL	7816	7030	6428	5919	5471	5067	4694	4348	4022	3715	3422
Neamt-Model_22	Forecast	5589	5589	5589	5589	5589	5589	5589	5589	5589	5589	5589
	UCL	6894	7434	7848	8197	8505	8783	9039	9277	9501	9713	9914
	LCL	4285	3745	3330	2981	2673	2395	2139	1901	1677	1465	1264
Suceava-Model_23	Forecast	8125	8416	8706	8997	9287	9578	9868	10159	10449	10740	11030
	UCL	9822	10815	11644	12389	13080	13733	14356	14956	15538	16103	16656
	LCL	6429	6017	5768	5604	5494	5423	5380	5361	5361	5376	5404
Vaslui-Model_24	Forecast	4442	4603	4765	4927	5088	5250	5411	5573	5735	5896	6058
	UCL	5556	6179	6695	7156	7580	7980	8360	8725	9078	9421	9755
	LCL	3327	3027	2834	2697	2596	2520	2463	2421	2391	2372	2361
Sud-Est-Model_25	Forecast	32411	32411	32411	32411	32411	32411	32411	32411	32411	32411	32411
	UCL	37977	40282	42051	43543	44857	46044	47137	48153	49108	50012	50871

	LCL	26845	24540	22771	21280	19966	18778	17686	16669	15714	14811	13952
Braila-Model_26	Forecast	4171	4171	4171	4171	4171	4171	4171	4171	4171	4171	4171
	UCL	5128	5456	5715	5937	6134	6313	6479	6633	6778	6915	7046
	LCL	3213	2885	2626	2404	2207	2028	1862	1708	1563	1426	1295
Buzau-Model_27	Forecast	6155	6155	6155	6155	6155	6155	6155	6155	6155	6155	6155
	UCL	7156	7570	7888	8156	8392	8606	8802	8985	9157	9319	9474
	LCL	5154	4740	4422	4154	3918	3704	3508	3325	3153	2991	2836
Constanta-Model_28	Forecast	9199	9199	9199	9199	9199	9199	9199	9199	9199	9199	9199
	UCL	10793	11268	11653	11986	12283	12553	12803	13038	13258	13467	13667
	LCL	7605	7130	6745	6412	6116	5845	5595	5361	5140	4931	4732
Galati-Model_29	Forecast	6648	6648	6648	6648	6648	6648	6648	6648	6648	6648	6648
	UCL	7706	8144	8481	8764	9014	9240	9448	9641	9823	9994	10158
	LCL	5590	5152	4815	4532	4282	4056	3848	3655	3473	3302	3138
Tulcea-Model_30	Forecast	2059	2059	2059	2059	2059	2059	2059	2059	2059	2059	2059
	UCL	2384	2486	2568	2638	2701	2758	2811	2860	2907	2951	2992
	LCL	1733	1632	1550	1480	1417	1360	1307	1258	1211	1167	1125
Vrancea-Model_31	Forecast	4282	4282	4282	4282	4282	4282	4282	4282	4282	4282	4282
	UCL	5152	5513	5789	6022	6228	6414	6584	6743	6893	7034	7168
	LCL	3412	3051	2775	2542	2336	2151	1980	1821	1672	1530	1396
Macroregiunea trei-Model_32	Forecast	80897	80897	80897	80897	80897	80897	80897	80897	80897	80897	80897
	UCL	89953	93703	96581	99007	101145	103078	104855	106509	108062	109532	110929
	LCL	71842	68091	65213	62787	60649	58717	56940	55285	53732	52262	50865
Sud - Muntenia- Model_33	Forecast	36477	36477	36477	36477	36477	36477	36477	36477	36477	36477	36477
	UCL	43420	46296	48503	50363	52003	53484	54847	56115	57307	58433	59505
	LCL	29534	26658	24451	22591	20951	19470	18107	16839	15647	14521	13449
Arges-Model_34	Forecast	8162	8162	8162	8162	8162	8162	8162	8162	8162	8162	8162

	UCL	9678	10305	10787	11193	11551	11875	12172	12449	12709	12955	13189
	LCL	6646	6019	5537	5131	4773	4449	4152	3875	3615	3369	3135
Calarasi-Model_35	Forecast	3552	3647	3741	3836	3931	4026	4121	4216	4310	4405	4500
	UCL	4048	4349	4602	4829	5041	5242	5434	5620	5800	5975	6147
	LCL	3055	2944	2881	2843	2821	2810	2807	2811	2821	2835	2853
Dâmbovita-Model_36	Forecast	6138	6382	6626	6870	7114	7358	7602	7846	8090	8334	8578
	UCL	7589	8434	9139	9772	10359	10912	11441	11950	12443	12923	13391
	LCL	4687	4330	4113	3968	3869	3804	3763	3742	3737	3745	3765
Giurgiu-Model_37	Forecast	2349	2349	2349	2349	2349	2349	2349	2349	2349	2349	2349
	UCL	2712	2862	2977	3074	3160	3237	3308	3374	3437	3495	3551
	LCL	1986	1836	1721	1624	1538	1461	1390	1324	1261	1203	1147
Ialomita-Model_38	Forecast	2910	2991	3072	3153	3234	3314	3395	3476	3557	3638	3719
	UCL	3404	3690	3928	4141	4339	4525	4703	4874	5040	5201	5359
	LCL	2416	2292	2216	2164	2128	2104	2087	2078	2074	2075	2079
Prahova-Model_39	Forecast	9924	9924	9924	9924	9924	9924	9924	9924	9924	9924	9924
	UCL	11930	12761	13398	13936	14409	14838	15231	15598	15942	16267	16577
	LCL	7918	7087	6450	5912	5439	5010	4617	4250	3906	3581	3271
Teleorman-Model_40	Forecast	3862	3862	3862	3862	3862	3862	3862	3862	3862	3862	3862
	UCL	4788	5171	5466	5714	5932	6130	6311	6481	6639	6790	6933
	LCL	2936	2553	2258	2010	1792	1594	1413	1243	1085	934	791
Bucuresti - Ilfov-Model_41	Forecast	44420	44420	44420	44420	44420	44420	44420	44420	44420	44420	44420
	UCL	48429	50089	51363	52438	53384	54239	55026	55758	56446	57097	57715
	LCL	40411	38751	37477	36403	35456	34601	33814	33082	32394	31743	31125
Bucuresti-Model_42	Forecast	35964	35964	35964	35964	35964	35964	35964	35964	35964	35964	35964
	UCL	39432	40868	41970	42899	43718	44458	45139	45772	46367	46930	47465
	LCL	32496	31060	29958	29029	28210	27470	26789	26156	25561	24998	24463

Ilfov-Model_43	Forecast	8854	9253	9651	10049	10447	10846	11244	11642	12040	12439	12837
	UCL	9603	10312	10948	11547	12122	12680	13226	13761	14288	14808	15321
	LCL	8105	8193	8353	8551	8772	9011	9262	9523	9793	10070	10353
Macroregiunea patru-Model_44	Forecast	45424	45424	45424	45424	45424	45424	45424	45424	45424	45424	45424
	UCL	50445	52525	54121	55466	56651	57723	58708	59626	60487	61302	62077
	LCL	40403	38323	36727	35382	34197	33125	32140	31222	30361	29546	28771
Sud-Vest Oltenia-Model_45	Forecast	24058	24058	24058	24058	24058	24058	24058	24058	24058	24058	24058
	UCL	29048	31115	32701	34038	35216	36281	37261	38172	39029	39838	40609
	LCL	19068	17001	15415	14078	12900	11835	10855	9944	9087	8278	7507
Dolj-Model_46	Forecast	8487	8487	8487	8487	8487	8487	8487	8487	8487	8487	8487
	UCL	9841	10402	10832	11195	11514	11803	12069	12316	12549	12768	12977
	LCL	7133	6572	6142	5779	5460	5171	4905	4658	4425	4206	3997
Gorj-Model_47	Forecast	4035	4035	4035	4035	4035	4035	4035	4035	4035	4035	4035
	UCL	4868	5213	5478	5701	5898	6076	6239	6392	6535	6670	6798
	LCL	3202	2857	2592	2369	2172	1994	1831	1678	1535	1400	1272
Mehedinti-Model_48	Forecast	2684	2684	2684	2684	2684	2684	2684	2684	2684	2684	2684
	UCL	3494	3788	4019	4215	4388	4546	4691	4827	4954	5075	5190
	LCL	1874	1580	1350	1154	980	822	677	542	414	294	179
Olt-Model_49	Forecast	4334	4334	4334	4334	4334	4334	4334	4334	4334	4334	4334
	UCL	5243	5620	5909	6152	6367	6561	6739	6905	7061	7209	7349
	LCL	3425	3048	2759	2516	2301	2107	1929	1763	1607	1459	1319
Vâlcea-Model_50	Forecast	4531	4531	4531	4531	4531	4531	4531	4531	4531	4531	4531
	UCL	5699	6182	6554	6866	7142	7391	7620	7834	8034	8224	8404
	LCL	3363	2880	2508	2196	1920	1671	1442	1228	1028	838	658
Vest-Model_51	Forecast	21366	21366	21366	21366	21366	21366	21366	21366	21366	21366	21366
	UCL	24607	25950	26980	27849	28614	29305	29942	30534	31090	31616	32116
	LCL	18125	16782	15752	14883	14118	13427	12790	12198	11642	11116	10616

Arad-Model_52	Forecast	5939	5939	5939	5939	5939	5939	5939	5939	5939	5939	5939
	UCL	7148	7600	7952	8252	8517	8757	8978	9184	9378	9562	9736
	LCL	4729	4278	3925	3625	3360	3120	2899	2693	2499	2316	2141
Caras-Severin-Model_53	Forecast	2419	2419	2419	2419	2419	2419	2419	2419	2419	2419	2419
	UCL	2764	2907	3017	3110	3191	3265	3332	3396	3455	3511	3564
	LCL	2074	1931	1821	1728	1647	1573	1506	1442	1383	1327	1274
Hunedoara-Model_54	Forecast	4570	4570	4570	4570	4570	4570	4570	4570	4570	4570	4570
	UCL	5364	5693	5945	6158	6345	6515	6670	6815	6952	7080	7203
	LCL	3776	3447	3195	2982	2795	2625	2470	2325	2188	2060	1937
Timis-Model_55	Forecast	8442	8442	8442	8442	8442	8442	8442	8442	8442	8442	8442
	UCL	9505	9945	10283	10568	10819	11046	11254	11449	11631	11803	11968
	LCL	7379	6939	6601	6316	6065	5838	5630	5435	5253	5081	4916

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